

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Mazouz**FIRST NAME:** Oumelkheir**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Starting an essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-2)
3. Writing the essay (EUCLID 2019, 3-4)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-14)
5. Writing aid (EUCLID Gulma 2019, 24-35)
6. Style guide (EUCLID Gulma 2019, 24-26)
7. Difference between American and British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)

UNDERSTANDING ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It has been long since I had to write an academic essay, so my skills have dulled, *and the course pack helped guide me to understand how to go about writing one. I learnt the tools that are required to write an academic essay with the understanding on how to go about it, and the appropriate grammatical tools.*

2) ESSAY WRITING

The course pack begins by reintroducing me to how to go about writing an essay, which begin by stating the purpose of an academic essay, which is to “persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). In other words, in the essay should convey the answer, and build on it to convince the reader to why you came to your conclusion.

a) Starting an essay

Before we begin writing, I understood that taking our time to understand the question. Understanding the question before we begin will allow the writer to create an initial plan to help guide the writer on the writer's research (ibid.).

Once an initial plan is made, the research phase should begin, where there would be an initial reading of the material and then a second reading, which is when you would take your notes. Although it is recommended to take notes during a second read, I personally prefer to take note while doing my first notes so that at my second read I remove any confusion or misconception I would have had. Nonetheless, taking notes is a crucial step, since it will probably be what you come back to while you are writing.

After gathering more knowledge on the given material, you will have more depth to the answer, and might change your understanding of the question and what you expected the answer to be. This means you should take a moment to reestablish a plan of attack on how to write your essay.

b) Writing the essay

Once you have gathered the information you need, it is time to put pen into paper. The format given in the book is standard and I tried to keep in mind while writing this essay;

- Introduction, a short beginning to the essay to introduce and give the reader a broad image of what to expect,
- Body, the bulk of the paper, where the writer goes into explain their point, and dive deeper into the conversation, and
- Conclusion, an ending that reiterates the purpose and the writer's thoughts on the topic at hand, re-broadening the argument (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Having understood that, once you start writing keep in my mind that your first go at writing the essay is nothing but a first draft. This simple reminder came in handy, reminding to keep calm and slowdown, because once I was done went back to read what I wrote. Finding few holes in my writing, I was able to fix it up to what I deemed acceptable.

c) Plagiarism

Other than writing the essay itself, the course back shed plenty of light on plagiarism and the importance of avoiding it. Plagiarism is to take others work and ideas as if it is your own, which is easy to mistakenly do. The fix is simple, which is through citations, the text went into great details explaining how to cite, and the different nuances on how to cite the work of others (EUCLID 2019, 5-6).

For the sake of simplicity, citing comes in two parts, if a block of text is written with an idea from another writer's text, then it is paraphrasing, and the writer should be cited with your references. If a work is copied word for word from a source, then it should be quoted, placing the quote between quotation marks and the writer will be both cited in the text right after the quote and in the references.

d) Writing aid

There are two more concepts that I want to bring forth, that I believe will help improve my writing down the road.

i) *Style Guide*

“A style guide is a mean of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2019, 24).

A style is something I never given any thought to, but this brought to my attention how helpful one could be. In certain cases where I might need to show the essence of a writer in my own writing or if I was to write for an organization a style guide will come in very handy.

ii) *Understanding the difference between American and British English*

I will not go into detail, but I do want to mention how the coursepack showed me how many differences there are between both academics' styles of writing. I used to think the differences only lie in the spelling, and now I know that there are some grammatical preferences which differ between them.

3) CONCLUSION

Through reading this coursepack I believe that I have a better understanding on how to write my own essay. It has given the confidence to tackle my first essay with Euclid, especially with a response paper that is about writing an essay.

REFERENCES

Cleenewreck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.